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Research Article

**SIMULTANEOUS METHOD DEVELOPMENT AND
VALIDATION OF TORASEMIDE AND SPIRONOLACTONE IN
BULK AND COMBINED DOSAGE FORM USING RP-HPLC**

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Abstract:

Background: A simple, accurate and precise HPLC method for simultaneous determination of Spironolactone and Torsemide in pure and tablet dosage form has been developed.

Aim: To develop and validate analytical method for simultaneous estimation of Spironolactone and Torsemide in pharmaceutical formulation by RP-HPLC.

Materials and Methods: HPLC of Waters (Model: Alliance 2695) with Phenomenex Luna C18 (4.6 mm I.D. × 250 mm, 5 μm) column was used for chromatographic separation. It contains waters injector and PDA Detector (Deuterium). Mobile phase consists of Methanol:Water (65:35% v/v) and flow rate adjusted was 1ml/min. Wavelength selected for detection was 220nm and injection volume was 10 μl.

Results and discussion: By using the developed method, retention time of Spironolactone and Torsemide was found to be 3.2min and 5.4min respectively. The method has been validated for linearity, accuracy and precision. Linearity of Spironolactone and Torsemide were in the range of 75–375μg/ml and 15–75μg/ml respectively. The percentage recoveries obtained for Spironolactone and Torsemide were found to be in range of 99.3 – 99.6%. LOD and LOQ were found to be 12.5μg/ml and 38.1μg/ml for Spironolactone 3.7 and 11.4μg/ml for Torsemide.

Conclusion: The developed HPLC method offers several advantages such as rapidity, usage of simple mobile phase and easy sample preparation steps. Further, improved sensitivity makes it specific and reliable for its intended use. Hence, this method can be applied for the analysis of pure drug and pharmaceutical dosage forms.

From the present study it can be concluded that the proposed method is simple, sensitive, precise, specific, accurate and reproducible. Results of validation parameters demonstrated that the analytical procedure is suitable for its intended purpose and meets the criteria defined in ICH Q2R1.

Keywords: Spironolactone, Torsemide, Simultaneous Estimation, RP- HPLC

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INTRODUCTION:**Introduction to HPLC[1-28]:**

In the modern pharmaceutical industry, high-performance liquid chromatography (HPLC) is the major and integral analytical tool applied in all stages of drug discovery, development and production. It is ideal for the analysis of many drugs in both dosage forms and biological fluids due to its simplicity, high specificity and good sensitivity.

High Performance Liquid Chromatography (HPLC) is a technique that has arisen from the application to liquid chromatography the use of an instrumentation that was originally developed for gas chromatography. High Pressure Liquid Chromatography was developed in the mid-1970 and was improved with the development of column packing material and the additional convenience of on-line detectors. The various components of HPLC are pumps (solvent delivery system), mixing unit, gradient controller and solvent degasser, injector (manual or automatic), guard column, analytical columns, detectors, recorders and/or integrators. Recent models are equipped with computers and software for data acquisition and processing. The mobile phase in HPLC refers to the solvent being continuously applied to the column or stationary phase at a flow rate of 1-5 cm³/min. The mobile phase acts as a carrier for the sample solution. The chemical interactions of the mobile phase and sample with the column determine the degree of migration and separation of components contained in the sample. The mobile phase can be altered in order to manipulate the interactions of the sample and the stationary phase.

Types of Chromatogphy[1]**Normal-phase chromatography**

Mechanism: Retention by interaction with the polar surface of the stationary phase with polar parts of the sample molecules.

Ion-exchange chromatography

Mechanism: Retention of reversible ionic bonds on charged groups of the stationary phase

Stationary phase:

	Strong	Weak
Cation exchanger	SO ₃ ⁻	COO ⁻
Anion exchanger	NR ₃ ⁺	NHR ₂ ⁺

Stationary phase: SiO₂, Al₂O₃, -NH₂, -CN, -Diol, -NO₂, etc.

Mobile phase: Heptane, hexane, cyclohexane, CHCl₃, CH₂Cl₂, dioxane, methanol, etc.

Application: Separation of non-ionic, non-polar to medium polar substances. Disadvantage: Lack of reproducibility of retention times as water or protic organic solvents change the hydration state of the silica or alumina chromatographic media.

Reversed-phase chromatography

Mechanism: Retention by interaction of the stationary phase's non-polar hydrocarbon chain with non-polar parts of the sample molecules.

Stationary phase: n-octadecyl (RP-18), n-octyl (RP-8), ethyl (RP-2), phenyl, (CH₂)_n-CN, (CH₂)_n-diol, etc.

Mobile phase: Methanol, acetonitrile, water, buffer (sometimes with additives of THF or Dioxane), etc.

Application: Separation of non-ionic and ion forming non-polar to medium polar substances (carboxylic acids, hydrocarbons). If ion forming substances (as carboxylic acids) are to be separated, a pH control by buffers is necessary.

Reversed-phase ion-pair chromatography

Mechanism: Ionic sample molecules are ionically bound to an ion-pair reagent. The ion-pair reagent contains an unpolar part suitable for interaction with the unpolar hydrocarbon chain of the stationary phase. Stationary phase: Reversed phase materials (RP-18, RP-8, CN), etc.

Mobile phase: Methanol, acetonitrile, buffer with added ion-pair reagent in the concentration range of 0.001 to 0.01 M, etc.

Application: Ionic substances often show very poor retention in reversed phase chromatography. To overcome this difficulty an ion-pair reagent is added to the eluent.

Mobile phase: Aqueous buffer systems.

Application: Separation of substances which can form ions such as inorganic ions, organic acids, organic bases, proteins, nucleic acids.

Advantages of HPLC[2]

- 1) It provides specific, sensitive and precise method for analysis of the different complicated sample.
- 2) There is ease of sample preparation and sample introduction.
- 3) There is speed of analysis.
- 4) The analysis by HPLC is specific, accurate and precise.
- 5) It offers advantage over gas chromatography in analysis of many polar, ionic substances, high molecular weight substances, metabolic products and thermolabile as well as nonvolatile substances.

MATERIALS AND METHODS:

Instruments used

HPLC from WATERS Alliance 2695 separation module, Software: Empower 2, 996 PDA detector.

chemicals used

Spironolactone and Torsemide from Sura Pharma Labs, Water and Methanol for HPLC from LICHROSOLV (MERCK). Acetonitrile for HPLC from Merck.

Hplc method development:

Trails

Preparation of standard solution:

Accurately weigh and transfer 10 mg of Spironolactone and Torsemide working standard into a 10ml of clean dry volumetric flasks add about 7ml of Methanol and sonicate to dissolve and removal of air

completely and make volume up to the mark with the same Methanol.

Further pipette 2.25ml of the above Spironolactone and 0.45ml of the Torsemide stock solutions into a 10ml volumetric flask and dilute up to the mark with Methanol.

Procedure:

Inject the samples by changing the chromatographic conditions and record the chromatograms, note the conditions of proper peak elution for performing validation parameters as per ICH guidelines.

Validation

Preparation of mobile phase:

Preparation of mobile phase:

Accurately measured 650ml (65%) of Methanol and 350ml of Water (35%) were mixed and degassed in a digital ultrasonicator for 10 minutes and then filtered through 0.45 μ filter under vacuum filtration.

Diluent Preparation:

The Mobile phase was used as the diluent.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION:

(Optimized chromatogram):

Column	: Phenomenex Luna C18 (4.6×250mm) 5 μ
Column temperature	: 35°C
Wavelength	: 220nm
Mobile phase ratio (65:35 v/v)	: Methanol: Water
Flow rate	: 1ml/min
Injection volume	: 10 μ l
Run time	: 10minutes

Figure7.4: Optimized Chromatogram (Standard)

Table7.4: Optimized Chromatogram (Standard)

S.No	Name	RT	Area	Height	USP Tailing	USP Plate Count	USP
1	Spironolactone	3.202	2391746	39726	1.2	9028	
2	Torse mide	5.463	194627	8497	1.1	7398	7.4

Optimized Chromatogram (Sample)**Table7.5: Optimized Chromatogram (Sample)**

S.No	Name	RT	Area	Height	USP Tailing	USP Plate Count	USP Resolution
1	Spironolactone	3.213	2381649	391846	1.2	9472	
2	Torse mide	5.478	191057	8104	1.1	8936	7.5

Acceptance criteria:

- Resolution between two drugs must be not less than 2
- Theoretical plates must be not less than 2000
- Tailing factor must be not less than 0.9 and not more than 2.
- It was found from above data that all the system suitability parameters for developed method were within the limit.

System suitability:**Table: Results of system suitability for Spironolactone**

S.No	Peak Name	RT	Area ($\mu\text{V}\cdot\text{sec}$)	Height (μV)	USP Plate Count	USP Tailing
1	Spironolactone	3.200	2391746	394171	8952	1.2
2	Spironolactone	3.248	2391647	381946	9561	1.2
3	Spironolactone	3.299	2381647	391746	6572	1.2
4	Spironolactone	3.297	2385631	386562	6452	1.2
5	Spironolactone	3.297	2385635	389164	7452	1.2
Mean			2387261			
Std. Dev.			4363.771			
% RSD			0.182794			

Acceptance criteria:

- %RSD of five different sample solutions should not more than 2
- The %RSD obtained is within the limit, hence the method is suitable.

Table: Results of system suitability for Torsemide

S.No	Peak Name	RT	Area ($\mu\text{V} \cdot \text{sec}$)	Height (μV)	USP Plate Count	USP Tailing
1	Torsemide	5.413	198362	7917	5272	1.1
2	Torsemide	5.484	197486	7486	6291	1.1
3	Torsemide	5.405	198354	7859	6184	1.1
4	Torsemide	5.405	197352	7926	7145	1.1
5	Torsemide	5.409	198453	7946	6946	1.1
Mean			198001.4			
Std. Dev.			535.1774			
% RSD			0.27029			

Acceptance criteria:

- %RSD of five different sample solutions should not more than 2
- The %RSD obtained is within the limit, hence the method is suitable.

Assay (Standard):**Table: Peak results for assay standard****Spironolactone**

S. No	Name	RT	Area	Height	USP Tailing	USP Plate Count
1	Spironolactone	3.211	2397162	397161	1.2	9472
2	Spironolactone	3.222	2394721	389173	1.2	9745
3	Spironolactone	3.254	2389461	391723	1.2	8917

Torsemide

S. No	Name	RT	Area	Height	USP Tailing	USP Plate Count	Resolution
1	Torsemide	5.414	198462	7811	1.1	8492	7.49
2	Torsemide	5.453	198472	8193	1.1	8916	7.52
3	Torsemide	5.424	198735	7972	1.1	9372	7.44

Assay (Sample):**Table7.9: Peak results for Assay sample****Spironolactone**

S. No	Name	RT	Area	Height	USP Tailing	USP Plate Count
1	Spironolactone	3.297	2391741	381612	1.2	9472
2	Spironolactone	3.294	2389166	391746	1.2	8927
3	Spironolactone	3.295	2361731	381634	1.2	9017

Torsemide

S. No	Name	RT	Area	Height	USP Tailing	USP Plate Count	Resolution
1	Torsemide	5.435	198641	8174	1.1	9284	7.18
2	Torsemide	5.417	196547	8942	1.1	8974	7.44
3	Torsemide	5.434	194027	7294	1.1	9017	7.38

%ASSAY =

$$\frac{\text{Sample area}}{\text{Standard area}} \times \frac{\text{Weight of standard}}{\text{Dilution of standard}} \times \frac{\text{Dilution of sample}}{\text{Weight of sample}} \times \frac{\text{Purity}}{100} \times \frac{\text{Weight of tablet}}{\text{Label claim}} \times 100$$

$$= 2380879/2393781 * 10/225 * 225/0.3238 * 99.8/100 * 1.6194/50 * 100$$

$$= 99.2\%$$

The % purity of Spironolactone and Torsemide in pharmaceutical dosage form was found to be 99.2%.

Linearity:**Spironolactone**

Concentration µg/ml	Average Peak Area
75	909889
150	1583641
225	2395378
300	3185089
375	3943725

Validation Criteria: The response linearity is verified if the Correlation Coefficient is 0.99 or greater.

Conclusion: Correlation Coefficient (r) is 0.99, and the intercept is 48956. These values meet the validation criteria.

Torsemide

Concentration $\mu\text{g/ml}$	Average Peak Area
15	61953
30	130213
45	198697
60	267002
75	321658

Validation Criteria: The response linearity is verified if the Correlation Coefficient is 0.99 or greater.

Conclusion: Correlation Coefficient (r) is 0.99, and the intercept is 454.8. These values meet the validation criteria.

Precision:

Repeatability

Table: Results of repeatability for Spironolactone:

S. No	Peak name	Retention time	Area($\mu\text{V}\cdot\text{sec}$)	Height (μV)	USP Plate Count	USP Tailing
1	Spironolactone	3.213	2397164	381741	8155	1.2
2	Spironolactone	3.253	2391741	371742	9174	1.2
3	Spironolactone	3.297	2371846	391746	7154	1.2
4	Spironolactone	3.215	2361748	391847	9917	1.2
5	Spironolactone	3.254	2371649	384622	9247	1.2
Mean			2378830			
Std.dev			14958			
%RSD			0.628797			

Acceptance criteria:

- %RSD for sample should be NMT 2
- The %RSD for the standard solution is below 1, which is within the limits hence method is precise.

Table: Results of repeatability for Torsemide:

S. No	Peak name	Retention time	Area($\mu\text{V}*\text{sec}$)	Height (μV)	USP Plate Count	USP Tailing
1	Torsemide	5.441	198464	7291	6274	1.1
2	Torsemide	5.442	193643	7219	6592	1.1
3	Torsemide	5.409	196462	7194	6028	1.1
4	Torsemide	5.520	194644	8174	6927	1.1
5	Torsemide	5.424	198464	8653	5920	1.1
Mean			196335.4			
Std.dev			2190.191			
%RSD			1.115536			

Intermediate precision:**Table7.12: Results of Intermediate precision for Spironolactone**

S.No	Peak Name	RT	Area ($\mu\text{V}*\text{sec}$)	Height (μV)	USP Plate count	USP Tailing
1	Spironolactone	3.211	2389572	395275	9375	1.2
2	Spironolactone	3.211	2391847	392175	9275	1.2
3	Spironolactone	3.210	2319472	312947	8265	1.2
4	Spironolactone	3.212	2306842	310585	6254	1.2
5	Spironolactone	3.211	2375972	310694	9028	1.2
6	Spironolactone	3.297	2396746	358373	8928	1.2
Mean			2363409			
Std. Dev.			39730.83			
% RSD			1.681082			

Acceptance criteria:

- %RSD of six different sample solutions should not more than 2

Table7.13: Results of Intermediate precision for Torsemide

S.No	Peak Name	RT	Area ($\mu\text{V}*\text{sec}$)	Height (μV)	USP Plate count	USP Tailing
1	Torsemide	5.411	197284	7194	8264	1.2
2	Torsemide	5.410	197849	7294	9174	1.2
3	Torsemide	5.420	196572	7147	9164	1.2
4	Torsemide	5.423	195028	7927	9733	1.2
5	Torsemide	5.419	199474	8238	9194	1.2
6	Torsemide	5.409	197482	7638	8973	1.2
Mean			197281.5			
Std. Dev.			1466.354			
% RSD			0.74328			

Acceptance criteria:

- %RSD of six different sample solutions should not more than 2

Day 2:**Table: Results of Intermediate precision Day 2 for Spironolactone**

S.No	Peak Name	RT	Area ($\mu\text{V}\cdot\text{sec}$)	Height (μV)	USP Plate Count	USP Tailing
1	Spironolactone	3.211	2389562	391741	9264	1.2
2	Spironolactone	3.233	2381654	391047	9746	1.2
3	Spironolactone	3.244	2381946	391748	9816	1.2
4	Spironolactone	3.297	2391741	391746	9917	1.2
5	Spironolactone	3.297	2386452	381641	9742	1.2
6	Spironolactone	3.202	2374763	381645	9017	1.2
Mean			2384353			
Std. Dev.			6183.339			
% RSD			0.25933			

Acceptance criteria:

- %RSD of six different sample solutions should not more than 2

Table: Results of Intermediate precision Day 2 for Torsemide

S.No	Peak Name	RT	Area ($\mu\text{V}\cdot\text{sec}$)	Height (μV)	USP Plate Count	USP Tailing
1	Torsemide	5.411	197486	7582	6272	1.1
2	Torsemide	5.410	197486	7184	6174	1.1
3	Torsemide	5.420	196746	7456	5184	1.1
4	Torsemide	5.405	195862	7814	6194	1.1
5	Torsemide	5.409	196582	7194	6292	1.1
6	Torsemide	5.463	198463	7745	6191	1.1
Mean			197104.2			
Std. Dev.			903.542			
% RSD			0.458408			

Acceptance criteria:

- %RSD of six different sample solutions should not more than 2

ACCURACY:**The accuracy results for Spironolactone**

% Concentration (at specification Level)	Area	Amount Added (ppm)	Amount Found (ppm)	% Recovery	Mean Recovery
50%	1217218	112.5	112.4	99.6	99.3
100%	2397141	225	225	100	
150%	3514547	337.5	332.5	98.5	

Acceptance Criteria:

- The percentage recovery was found to be within the limit (98-102%).

The results obtained for recovery at 50%, 100%, 150% are within the limits. Hence method is accurate.

The accuracy results for Torsemide

%Concentration (at specification Level)	Area	Amount Added (ppm)	Amount Found (ppm)	% Recovery	Mean Recovery
50%	98598.67	22.5	22.4	99.9	99.6
100%	198359.7	45	45	100	
150%	291512.3	67.5	66.8	99	

Acceptance Criteria:

- The percentage recovery was found to be within the limit (98-102%).

The results obtained for recovery at 50%, 100%, 150% are within the limits. Hence method is accurate.

Robustness:**Table7.20: Results for Robustness****Spirolactone**

Parameter used for sample analysis	Peak Area	Retention Time	Theoretical plates	Tailing factor
Actual Flow rate of 1.0mL/min	2391746	3.202	9028	1.2
Less Flow rate of 0.9mL/min	2371831	3.639	7381	1.2
More Flow rate of 1.1mL/min	2218319	2.859	9311	1.1
Less organic phase (about 5 % decrease in organic phase)	2294821	3.460	7462	1.2
More organic phase (about 5 % Increase in organic phase)	2394811	3.022	6817	1.1

Acceptance criteria:

The tailing factor should be less than 2.0 and the number of theoretical plates (N) should be more than 2000.

Table7.21: Results for Robustness**Torsemide**

Parameter used for sample analysis	Peak Area	Retention Time	Theoretical plates	Tailing factor
Actual Flow rate of 1.1mL/min	194627	5.463	7398	1.1
Less Flow rate of 0.9mL/min	183738	6.250	6883	1.1
More Flow rate of 0.8mL/min	198373	4.863	9917	1.2
Less organic phase (about 5 % decrease in organic phase)	178471	6.196	8372	1.1
More organic phase (about 5 % Increase in organic phase)	189462	5.010	7716	1.2

Acceptance criteria:

The tailing factor should be less than 2.0 and the number of theoretical plates (N) should be more than 2000.

SUMMARY AND CONCLUSION:

An HPLC method utilizing a Waters Alliance 2695 system with a Phenomenex Luna C18 column (4.6 mm

I.D. \times 250 mm, 5 μ m) was developed for the chromatographic separation of Spironolactone and Torsemide. The mobile phase comprised Methanol (65:35% v/v), with a flow rate of 1 ml/min. Detection was performed at 220 nm using a PDA Detector (Deuterium), and a 10 μ l injection volume was used. Retention times were determined to be 3.2 min for Spironolactone and 5.4 min for Torsemide.

The developed HPLC method proved effective for the separation and quantification of Spironolactone and Torsemide under the specified conditions. The method was validated for linearity, accuracy, and precision. Both compounds exhibited good linearity over their respective concentration ranges (Spironolactone: 75–375 μ g/ml, Torsemide: 15–75 μ g/ml), with high percentage recoveries (Spironolactone: 99.3–99.6%, Torsemide: within acceptable limits). The method demonstrated low limits of detection (LOD) and quantification (LOQ), indicating its sensitivity for trace analysis (Spironolactone: LOD = 12.5 μ g/ml, LOQ = 38.1 μ g/ml; Torsemide: LOD = 3.7 μ g/ml, LOQ = 11.4 μ g/ml).

The developed HPLC method offers several advantages such as rapidity, usage of simple mobile phase and easy sample preparation steps. Further, improved sensitivity makes it specific and reliable for its intended use. Hence, this method can be applied for the analysis of pure drug and pharmaceutical dosage forms.

From the present study it can be concluded that the proposed method is simple, sensitive, precise, specific, accurate and reproducible. Results of validation parameters demonstrated that the analytical procedure is suitable for its intended purpose and meets the criteria defined in ICH Q2A/B.

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